

FACTORS AFFECTING MORBIDITY AND MORTALITY OF PERINATAL DAIRY CALVES

Champak Bhakat*

National Dairy Research Institute, Karnal-132001, Haryana.

ABSTRACT

The morbidity and mortality in perinatal dairy calves amount to a great economical loss to a dairy herd. The environment at calving place affect calf health through stress and exposure to disease agents. The housing can affect the development of disease in a calf in many ways. The mortality is significantly lower for calves housed in stanchion barns than in a separate calf barn or in part of the loose housing. There is a significant increase in survival rates of calves raised in an area separate from the calving stalls. Bringing calves from different farms tend to increase the disease rate. Perinatal calf mortality rate increases during peak winter and peak summer with higher percentage in winter than summer. Early or delayed weaning increase morbidity and mortality rates. The herd average milk production is negatively correlated with mortality. Some other important factors viz: frequency of feeding, liquid diet, waste milk, perinatal care, navel treatment of calf, preventive practices of dam, herd size, sex and birth weight of calf, inherited congenital and non-congenital defects etc influence the morbidity and mortality of perinatal dairy calf. Some economical and effective control measures should be adopted to reduce perinatal calf morbidity and mortality. The calf mortality rate on a farm can be reduced with a minimum of effort by assisting colostrum intake to those calves which has a difficult birth.

Key words : Morbidity, mortality, calf, dairy herd, control measures.

Introduction

Health disorders in perinatal dairy calves greatly affect the economics of herd production. A diseased animal is also dangerous even to human health due to transmission of disease to human beings. The factors which influence the host, agent and environment will affect the occurrence of disease. Because of multiple effects and interactions, any change in a risk factor should be viewed in the context of total effect. Disease frequency can be measured by proportional morbidity, risk rates and true rates or incidence density measures. Calf mortality rate is the number of calves dead divided by the number of calves at risk of dying. The objective of this paper is to narrate environmental and managerial factors as they relate to morbidity and mortality in dairy calves during the first six months of life.

Environmental Factors

Calving area

There is evidence to indicate that the environment at calving will affect calf health through stress and exposure to disease agents. The pre-partum stress in the dam may influence immunoglobulin absorption by the newborn calf

(Stott, 1980). Calves born in stanchions and loose housing are more likely to develop diarrhoea than those born in calving pens, mainly due to increased environmental contamination. In the cold northern USA, during winter annual death losses of calf are more in herds where temperature of the calving facilities is approximately same as outside temperature. Where cows calved in heated facilities, during wintertime, annual death losses decreased to significant level. So it is recommended that clean, well-maintained, individual calving pens be provided and providing of heated calving areas may also be important during wintertime.

Calf housing

It is generally accepted that housing can affect the development of disease in a calf in many ways (Roy, 1980). Inadequate ventilation, improper climate control, poorly constructed or maintained facilities will all induce stress in calves. Overcrowding can increase the calf's exposure to disease agents while certain environments will stimulate the growth or preservation of disease agents. In addition, there is evidence that calf housing influences the level of serum IgG in 1-30-day-old calves (Norheim and Simenser, 1985).

E-Mail: bhakat@scientist.com

*Presently working as Scientist (senior-scale) and In charge C.M Unit, NRCC, Bikaner-334001, Rajasthan

Type of calf housing

Calf mortality is significantly lower for calves housed in stanchion barns than in a separate calf barn or in part of the loose housing. There is a significant increase in survival rates of calves raised in an area separate from the calving stalls. The improved housing for calf at an organised farm (NDRI) is having cover and open area. Cover area is required to protect from extreme climate where as open area is needed for sunlight and as an exercise place for obtaining proper growth. The climatic conditions inside calf house is greatly affect the desirability of certain housing factors. The insulation is more important in a colder climate. Type of housing can influence other risk factors such as cleanliness, air quality and relative humidity, which ultimately influence calf mortality.

New environment

It has been generally accepted that bringing calves from different farms will tend to increase the disease rate. This is due to increased stress in the calf from handling, movement into a different environment and establishment of a new order of social dominance. Another mechanism by which this could occur is through exposure to agents to which a calf has not been previously exposed and against which it has no immunity.

Seasonal effect

Calf mortality rate increases during peak winter and peak summer, with higher percentage in winter than summer. Relationship between mortality rate and season is presented in Fig. 1.

Managemental factors

Colostrum feeding practices

It is very essential to feed calf an adequate quantity of high quality colostrum soon after birth. That farms which has policies of attending calving and ensuring that calves received their first colostrums soon after birth are significantly less likely to experience mortality than farms which does not have these policies. Calves receiving colostrum from the dam has a lower calf mortality rate than calves receiving colostrum from a bucket. This is attributed to a benefit derived from consuming colostrum naturally. However, it is possible that sanitation of the bucket may have been important. The calf mortality rate on a farm can be reduced with a minimum effort by assisting colostrum intake to those calves which has a difficult birth.

Frequency of feeding

It is commonly recommended that calves should be fed twice daily to reduce mortality.

Feeding of liquid diet

Incase of feeding of milk replacer, it should be properly stored, mixed then fed according to need to reduce mortality.

Feeding of waste milk

The practice of feeding waste milk like mastitic or antibiotic tainted milk to calves in general, there is increase risk of disease to calves. Feeding antibiotic contaminated milk due to lack of consumption for it's poor palatability can decrease growth rate of calf.

Perinatal care

Calf mortality rate depends on type of person providing perinatal care. Mortality rate increases when hired labour is responsible for calf care as compared to family members. It has noted that calf mortality rate is the lowest when owner's mother or wife used to take care for their calves.

Weaning age

Early or delayed weaning increase morbidity and mortality rates. The effect of age at which a calf is weaned has been considered as important factor. James *et al.* (1984) reported that losses were 1.5 % higher in herds where calves were weaned after 8 weeks of age. There must be an optimum time at which weaning should be accomplished.

Navel treatment of calf

Treatment of the navel has long been a recommended practice. The farm level, a policy of routine navel treatment has significant effect on morbidity rates. At the individual calf level, the effect of navel treatment is dependent on the substance used. Iodine is associated with prolonged treatments, while substances other than iodine or chlorhexidine are associated with a greater risk of being treated for pneumonia. Individual calves which required assistance at birth and navel treated properly are less likely to die than untreated calves.

Preventive practices of dam

Calves are less likely to die if their dams have been treated with vitamins A, D and E as compared to calves born from untreated dams. A study conducted by Walter-Toews *et al.* (1986) in a selenium deficient area and reported that a tendency for calves from selenium-treated dams to have a lower treatment rate for pneumonia within 28 days of birth.

Miscellaneous Factors

Herd size

Herd size itself should not have a biological effect on calf health. Rather, it may be a

measurement of other farm factors such as various herd owner attributes (i.e. attitudes, values or education level) or time available to observe and care for calves. The morbidity and mortality of calf increases in big herd if there is less care for perinatal calf.

Herd production level

The herd average milk production is negatively correlated with mortality. Correlation between herd average production and mortality (%) of calf is given in Fig. 2. This suggests that the factors, which account for higher production may also relate to a lower calf mortality rate. Higher production level in larger herd suggests there may be differences between herds of different sizes such as genetic potential, nutrition level or management skill.

Sex of calf

Sex of the calf may be a determinant of calf morbidity. Singh and Tomer (1989) reported that incidence of diarrhoea is comparatively high in female than male buffalo calves. Effect of calf's sex on incidence (%) of diarrhoea is presented in Fig. 3.

Inherited congenital and noncongenital defects

The following inherited congenital and non-congenital defects are generally found in dairy calf breeds.

Type	Cattle Breed	Defects
Congenital	Jersey	Bull dog calves Multiple eye defects. Congenital spasm
	Holstein Friesian	Hydrocephalus Smooth tongue Multiple ankylosis Umbilical hernia
Non-congenital	Jersey	Familial polycythaemia.
	Holstein Friesian	Porphyria.
	Brown Swiss	Epilepsy
	Jersey & Holstein Friesian	Osteo-arthritis.

Birth weight

Birth weight of calf inversely correlated with mortality rate. Influence of birth weight on mortality (%) of calf is presented in Fig. 4.

Incidence of diseases in perinatal dairy calf of organised herd

Average incidence of various diseases in buffalo calf of birth to 6 months age is presented in Table 1. The incidence of diarrhoea was highest followed by respiratory ailments, TDS etc in buffalo calf of 0 to 6 months age. Incidence (%) of respiratory ailments

in buffalo calf of NDRI and MDF herd is given in Table 2. Incidence of respiratory ailments in buffalo calf (0 to 3 months aged) was highest during winter season in both of herds. Morbidity pattern (%) of 0 to 6 months aged calf of NDRI's herd is given in Fig. 5. The morbidity and mortality in perinatal dairy calves amount to a great economical loss to a dairy herd. The great loss is mainly due to gastro-intestinal disorders. The 54.13% of total calves up to age of six months suffered with diarrhoea which is mainly caused by micro-organisms particularly *Escherichia coli*. Though *E. coli* is a natural inhabitant of intestines of all warm-blooded animals and harmless. But when an adverse debilitating factor lowers the resistance, infection can occur causing of inflammation of intestines and the calf starts suffering with diarrhoea. Tomar and Tripathi (1987) observed that the incidence of respiratory ailments, diarrhoea, and TDS was significantly higher in calves than in heifers and adult buffaloes, whereas the incidence of FMD was significantly higher in heifers than in calves and adults. The differences among age groups were less for tympany and eye troubles. Thus calves were more prone to the diarrhoea and respiratory ailments than heifers and adult buffaloes. Tomar and Tripathi (1986) reported that the heritability estimates for the incidence of diarrhoea obtained by the paternal half-sib correlation method were 0.328 ± 0.12 for the NDRI and 0.629 ± 0.16 for the MDF herds. The corresponding heritability estimates for the incidence of tympany were 0.07 ± 0.08 and 0.279 ± 0.12 , respectively.

Control Measures

Some economical and effective control measures should be adopted to reduce perinatal calf morbidity and mortality. The control measures are given as follows.

- (1) Properly cleaning and disinfections of calving pens.
- (2) Keep small number of animals in one common air space.
- (3) Provide natural ventilation.
- (4) Provide proper insulation of building.
- (5) Separation of age group of calves.
- (6) Colostrum feeding properly.
- (7) Provision of colostrum bank.
- (8) Follow all in all out principle.
- (9) Treatment of sick animal separately.
- (10) Follow proper way of mixing of newly arrived calves.
- (11) Keep sufficient quarantine period for newly arrived animal.
- (12) Follow practices of detail recording system of each and every aspect.

Table 3 presents vaccination schedule for calf which must be practiced in due course of time.

Mortality (%)

Fig. 1: Relationship between mortality rate and season (months)

Fig. 2: Correlation between herd average production and mortality (%) of calf

Fig. 5: Morbidity pattern (%) of 0 to 6 month aged calf at NDRI, herd.

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